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Equation-free bifurcation analysis of a stochastically excited Duffing oscillator

Zoltan Gabos^{a,*}, David A.W. Barton^b, Zoltan Dombovari^a^a MTA-BME Lendület Machine Tool Vibration Research Group, Department of Applied Mechanics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest H-1521, Hungary^b Department of Engineering Mathematics, University of Bristol, Merchant Venturers Building, Bristol BS8 1UB, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an extensive analysis of a stochastically excited one-degree-of-freedom mechanical system with cubic nonlinearity is presented. This is motivated by the need for realistic bifurcation analyses of stochastic dynamical systems, given that many physical applications contain significant time-varying uncertainty that can lead to drastically different solutions from the deterministic case. The proposed methodology is based on pseudo arc-length continuation combined with the moment-map method, which allows the investigation of dynamical systems with stochastic behaviour. It is shown that the introduction of noise in the excitation leads to the destabilisation of stable periodic orbits over time for the underlying system. For better interpretation and lower computational costs, instead of the combined stochastic continuation, the deterministic bifurcation diagram is modified with the detection and approximation of the mean first passage time of the stochastic system by introducing three different methods. Two semi-analytical approaches with Markov models, together with a completely numerical detection method for the mean first passage time, are compared to each other with similar results. The parameter sensitivity analysis and the comparison of the different methods support the proposed methodology for structural dynamic cases.

1. Introduction

The main aim of this work is to understand the fundamental behaviour of nonlinear mechanical systems under harmonic and stochastic forcing, and to present computationally inexpensive methods for their analysis. This can have significant impact in mechanical measurement practises, where weak nonlinearities are always present.

Structures subjected to dynamic effects are often designed to withstand the fatigue caused by long-term static and dynamic loading. The suppression of vibrations is especially important in the machine tool industry, where vibration amplitude directly affects surface quality and precision [1]. The assumption of linearity of the real structure provides the necessary predictability and measurability using conventional modal analysis techniques [2], however, this philosophy is very conservative and results in over-engineered designs. Due to their high cost, even machine tool builders experiment with alternative, e.g., welded structures, which can meet the necessary stiffness requirements. However, these alternative solutions, despite their stiffness, can behave in a nonlinear manner. For example, special operations like boring [3,4] can also load the structure in a nonlinear manner due to the design of the long arm used for tool clamping. Moreover, there is a growing trend in the machine tool industry to mainly use industrial robots for roughing operations where the surface might not be an issue. Here, predictability still has importance with

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zoltan.gabos@mm.bme.hu (Z. Gabos).

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respect to the generally flexible structure of the industrial robot [5,6] and, consequently, its large amplitude response and its effect on tool wear [7].

For other mechanical structures, stiffness is not always a requirement. Instead, they prioritise reducing mass as much as possible to achieve efficient designs, e.g., wing and blade designs [8,9]. These are slender elastic parts, where geometrical nonlinearities will inevitably appear. Even here, engineers seek methodologies for dynamic predictability by performing empirical tests somewhat related to the so-called backbone curve [10,11] or the nonlinear normal mode [12] approaches. To extract these descriptions, methods such as resonance decay [13,14] and restoring force methods [15,16] can be used.

The motivation of this study is to lay the groundwork for possible future measurement methods in which both the preload and the nonlinear resonance behaviour are captured. Here, the preload is ensured by the static component of periodic forcing, while the resonant behaviour is traced by continuation subjected to random (stochastic) excitation. For deterministic systems, numerical continuation is a general and well-developed analysis method [17,18] to follow the behaviour of the underlying nonlinear system with varying parameters. Continuation methods provide a convenient means to assess parameter-dependent behaviour, especially when analytical approaches fail. Continuation techniques overcome, or at least extend, the trial-and-error philosophy of numerical simulations and real engineering measurements. There are even approaches that combine numerical continuation with control techniques so that they can be applied directly to physical experiments [19].

In this work, an estimation method for a stochastically and harmonically excited nonlinear mechanical structure is introduced, where previously researched methods are combined to generate a relatively fast and reliable bifurcation analysis tool, which is a specialised numerical continuation technique that integrates statistical and multilevel simulation methods to well trace the stochastic system behaviour. The introduced methodology is similar to the method of stochastic averaging [20–22], however, the stochastic averaging method relies on a model with known system parameters, which is contradictory to the purpose of this study. Here, the possible transition of the methodology to measurement applications is a key feature, which requires the method to be independent of the describing equations of the system for which the combination of the so-called equation-free method [23] and statistical analysis is a sufficient solution. Furthermore, the introduction of noise with statistical calculations is a key part of reliability analysis in engineering [24], where the life expectancy of expensive or dangerous structures is crucial considering a proper confidence interval.

Summarising our interest is understanding the stochastic effects of forcing on nonlinear dynamical systems. In the aforementioned applications, such as machine tools, most of the cases have linearisable nonlinearities following the definition in [25]. The choice of using the Duffing oscillator as a nonlinearisable imitation of a practical system is a theoretical ‘worst case choice’ to try out the proposed methodology. We emphasise that the Duffing oscillator is only for imitating the real physical system, and further studies should be carried out to actually include measurement data as a true equation-free approach.

Equation-free methods are common in agent-based complex system characterisation and are suitable for systems where the macroscopic (overall) behaviour is unknown but the microscopic (individual motion) can be described. Such problems occur e.g. in gas dynamics [26] or in traffic jam modelling [23]. In addition, the moment map method [26] can be used instead of a general equation-free case, where the underlying system is low dimensional. The moments describe the average behaviour or the deviation from the average behaviour of the observed system as an example. The combination of this methodology with pseudo-arclength continuation shows how the noise from the stochastic excitation deforms the bifurcation diagram. The merged methodology and its use in structural dynamics are shown in this paper, where the destructive nature of the additional stochastic forcing term and the time dependency of the stable periodic orbits are presented.

However, the problem of increased calculation costs arises when the investigated system has to be observed over a longer time period and the magnitude of the stochastic forcing is large, compared to the harmonic term. In addition to the computational time of the combined moment-map continuation method, the question of short-time stability (known as metastability) can lead to the need of recalculating the bifurcation diagrams for every operation time interval (e.g. the time needed to remove material during a single milling operation) of the mechanical structure.

In this paper, three methods are introduced to avoid increasing the calculation costs. All of these procedures are based on the deterministic bifurcation analysis and use statistical tools, such as the process that satisfies the Markov property, also known as the Markov chain [27,28]. A similar approach has been studied in [29], where the transition probabilities between two states are calculated based on Lyapunov equations for the predator–prey model. This method also requires a precise mathematical description of the underlying system similarly to the previously mentioned existing methods. Note that the goal here is moving towards the derivation of the system parameters for a partly or completely unknown system.

The proposed methodology takes advantage of three approaches.

- A large number of numerical simulations with single trajectories, where the detection of the state transition denotes the loss of stability of a periodic orbit in time.
- Deterministic continuation-based semi-analytical methodology, where the distances between the stable and unstable periodic orbits are defining the transition probabilities in the Markov chain.
- Harmonic burst excitation-based semi-analytical methodology, where the magnitudes of the forcing are compared to the distance of the deterministic stable periodic orbit amplitudes. This is suitable for transferring the methodology to measurement applications in the future.

Based on the methods mentioned above, the bifurcation deformation can be interpreted by capturing the first passage time [30–32] of the state transitions. Meaning that the periodic solution is considered to be unstable if any or most of the transitions (depending on the actual problem definition) occur within the operation time of the mechanical system. The parameter sensitivity

of these proposed methods is also addressed and investigated in the last section, where the comparison of the numerical and semi-analytical methods shows the same behaviour of the observed system.

We note that there have been previous studies on stochastically-excited systems using the equation-free method [23] and the moment map method [26]. However, the results of all the aforementioned methods are highly dependent on the observation time Section 4.2. Moreover, an analytical approach that addresses the long-time behaviour description of stochastic systems using normal form calculus is presented in [33], where the past and future noise events influence the current slow dynamics addressed here by approximating boundaries and distributions in Markov Chain approach for the modelling of jump phenomenon underpinned by simulations in Sec. 5 as a sufficient engineering point of view. The following points summarise the advantages of our proposed approach.

- The proposed stochastic bifurcation method in this article is focused on response continuation in frequency domain with the intention for future measurement application.
- The computational time of the moment map method is reduced by simplifying the distribution definition Section 4.2.
- In Section 5.2 the introduction of the semi-analytical method provides a solution for the operational time-dependent stability analysis.
- In Section 5.2 a proposed measurement procedure is provided for the application of the semi-analytical method.

In addition, the recognised importance of the instantaneous frequency during state transition might lead to other nonlinear parameter quantification methods in the future, similar to the resonance decay method but for transient motions. This is also considered by other researchers in nonlinear dynamics [34].

2. Model

We base our work on a simple model of stochastic nonlinear behaviour, the Duffing equation with random forcing. This model describes typical nonlinear behaviour in the field of structural vibration problems and is simple enough to deal with the additional stochastic term in the forcing. Furthermore, it can also be considered to be an approximation of a multi-degree-of-freedom nonlinear system (in the absence of internal resonances).

Although this is the simplest model one could choose, it is important to understand the underlying nonlinear behaviour before stochastic excitation is introduced. There are many studies on this system, and deterministic solutions are known for the general Duffing equation [35,36]. On the other hand, some solutions of the stochastically excited Duffing oscillator are also known through the separation of the excitation [37] or by creating a force model, based on energy change during the operation [38].

The deterministic behaviour can be drastically changed due to the introduction of stochastic excitation. Although the related Markov chains and metastability of slow-fast dynamical systems are well documented in [39], the time dependency of the stochastic stability definition is presented in [32] for a pitchfork bifurcation. It is necessary to consider the stochastic behaviour when the underlying system is known to be sensitive to noise, as it can lead to severe problems when transiting between periodic orbits or equilibria.

We consider a single DoF mechanical model of the Duffing oscillator, where the spring characteristic $F_k(x)$ is nonlinear and the harmonic excitation is combined with some level of noise,

$$m \ddot{x}(t) + c \dot{x}(t) + F_k(x(t)) = F_{\text{stoch}}(t), \quad (1)$$

in which m is the mass, c is the damping and the local stiffness $k := \frac{dF_k}{dx}(\bar{x})$ around $\bar{x} \equiv 0$ can be normalised by the mass as usual. The mass normalised system is

$$\ddot{x}(t) + 2\zeta\omega_n\dot{x}(t) + \omega_n^2x(t) + \beta x^3(t) = \tilde{f}_0 \cos(\omega t) + \tilde{\sigma}W(t), \quad (2)$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c}{2\omega_n m}, \quad \omega_n^2 = \frac{k}{m}, \quad (3)$$

where ζ is the damping ratio, ω_n is the natural frequency, β is the so-called cubic nonlinear parameter, while $\tilde{f}_0 := F_0/m$ and ω are the rescaled amplitude and frequency of the forcing. The variable $\tilde{\sigma}$ is the level of stochastic forcing and $W(t)$ is the Wiener process, which describes a random walk around the equilibrium with normal distribution [40,41]. Eq. (2) can be compressed to a more compact form by rescaling the time as $t\omega_n \rightarrow t$:

$$x''(t) + 2\zeta x'(t) + x(t) + \mu x^3(t) = f_0 \cos(\lambda t) + \sigma W(t), \quad (4)$$

where μ is the nonlinear parameter, σ is the standard deviation of the Wiener process, while the forcing frequency is replaced by the frequency ratio, $\lambda = \omega/\omega_n$.

The first step towards the analysis of this stochastically excited Duffing oscillator is the discussion of stochastic time simulations. From a practical point of view, [42] offers a good overview of how to simulate stochastic processes. The general differential form of the stochastic differential equation can be formulated as

$$dx = f(x)dt + g(x)dW, \quad (5)$$

where $f(x)$ is the right-hand side (RHS) of the deterministic differential equation and $g(x)$ is the scaling function of the Wiener process. Throughout this study, we assume that $g(x)$ is constant, although in [26] it is considered to be state dependent. Our choice

is mostly due to simplicity, although, as with the locally linearisable nonlinear systems, we assume that for small noise levels and short time scales, $g(x)$ can be considered constant.

One discretisation of the corresponding differential equation subjected to stochastic effects is the so-called Euler Maruyama (EM) method. It can be useful for simulating numerical processes as an example. However, the practical approach here raises the problem of creating a continuous stochastic signal for the forcing of the system. The observed structure has its own deterministic dynamics (harmonically forced nonlinear beam) and the created discrete random signal (e.g. the signal is created in LabVIEW and fed into a shaker that is connected to the beam) is superposed on the deterministic behaviour. Interpretation of this idea through a MATLAB environment by using the ODE45 solver to solve the RHS and then adding the stochastic part to the solution can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_j &= \text{ODE45}_j(t_{\text{ODE}}) + g(\mathbf{X}_{j-1})(W(t_j) - W(t_{j-1})), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, L, \\ t_{\text{ODE}} &:= i \delta t \in [t_{j-1}, t_j], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_j := \mathbf{X}(t_j)$ is the state vector at $t_j \in [0, T]$, $T \in \mathbb{R}^+$. This is a simple solution for simulating the aforementioned system with the combination of harmonic and generated discrete random excitation considering low number of samples.

For a larger set of simulations, the above-mentioned methodology becomes immensely slow. Therefore, the SOSRA solver of the Julia environment will be used for further calculations, which is a higher-order stochastic solver.

3. Equation-free method

When a simple deterministic mechanical system is analysed, the equation of motion is usually known, and it explicitly describes the system behaviour. However, for some more complex models or stochastic simulations, the behaviour of the system cannot be calculated explicitly because the equations of motion are not known at the correct scale (e.g., micro versus macro descriptions). Moreover, there are challenges associated with the fact that, for a stochastic system, a single calculated trajectory does not fully describe the system. All of this is well documented in the work of [23].

There are different approaches to overcome the above-mentioned problem. One of them is to use the stochastic averaging method or the Fokker–Planck–Kolmogorov (FPK) equation associated with the SDE (Eq. (5)). This leads to an analysis of the density distribution of the state space through the probability density of the state variables [43,44]. Following previous studies, the time evolution of the probability density can be calculated for the Duffing oscillator by considering the transition probability of the periodic oscillation amplitude from one equilibrium to another. This means that we have to know the probability of changing state from an arbitrary state. Unfortunately, in most practical structural vibration cases, neither the transition probability nor the stable periodic orbits are exactly known prior to measurements. Our goal is to provide a method that could be potentially transferred to a measurement environment after introducing it through a known system, such as the Duffing oscillator.

To address both issues regarding transition probabilities and periodic solutions, the equation-free method [23] can be combined with the numerical continuation method [19]. The equation-free method provides an approximation for the time evolution of the slow system behaviour by using Monte Carlo (MC) simulations according to the fast system. This is now done through simulations of single trajectories for the known Duffing equation (Eq. (4)) but it can be replaced later by measuring single trajectories of an unknown system. In this way, the probability density of the state variables can be calculated without prior knowledge of the transition probabilities. Then, numerical continuation is used to find and map out periodic solutions of the nonlinear system as the critical parameters change. Finally, the combination of the two methods will give the bifurcation analysis of the state space, which can be transformed into a frequency–amplitude behaviour representation (resonance curve) of the underlying system. Note that the numerical nature of the equation-free and pseudo-arclength continuation method provides promising possibilities for future measurement approaches, due to the discrete sampling nature of measurements. For further information on the general formulation of the equation-free method by using MC simulations and information about its convergence criteria, the reader is guided to the study in [23].

Similarly to the general description in [23], the macroscopic and microscopic levels (slow and fast system behaviour, respectively) have to be defined. Here, the two levels evolved through time in the same Euclidean state space, which concludes that the general definition of the two levels would be unnecessary. In simple words, the given stochastic dynamics here is the fast system behaviour that can be averaged.

In [26], they suggest that for systems such as the Duffing oscillator, one can use the k th-order moment map as the evolution of the macroscopic state, while the microscopic level can be considered to be a series of simulations of the current state. That is due to the often observed quantities of interest being either averages or low-order moments (first-order: average, second-order: variance, etc.).

The moment map is defined through the linear flow of the probability densities of the SDE (Eq. (5)), where the nonlinearity comes from repeated projection onto the k th order moment space. This can be used for bifurcation analysis of low-dimensional systems, where the different moment maps can show different behaviours of the underlying system. The limitations of this method are related to the time dependency of the metastable periodic solutions [28,45]. That is, the outcome of the analysis is highly dependent on the given observation time of the phenomenon.

The process of creating moment maps can be summarised in three steps.

- **Evolution:** first, a system is needed that is appropriate for the simulation of single trajectories in time, where the single trajectories are the evolution of the underlying system by definition. Here, the observed system is governed by the equation of motion of the stochastically excited Duffing oscillator. However, single trajectories could be captured from measured signals in real applications.

- *Lifting*: this step defines the initial values for the evolution step by picking a point from the state space of the moment map and creating a set of initial values for every evolution. Two main definitions of the lifting operator are discussed and demonstrated in [26]. One of them is the *Dirac measure*, where the initial values are the current state from the state space of the moment map. This method defines the first-order moment map. The other approach is the *Gaussian measure*, where the evolution starts from a normally distributed neighbourhood of the current state from the moment map. This results in the second-order moment map. Note that the definition of the lifting operator is largely responsible for the outcome and computational time of the method as is discussed in Section 4.2.
- *Restriction*: the moment map is updated through this step, where the endpoints of the single trajectories from the evolution step are averaged and considered to be the new state on the moment map.

A compact illustration of the method can then be formed as:

$$lift \rightarrow evolve \rightarrow restrict.$$

Note that the moment map method is a specific case of the equation-free method, where the underlying system has few dimensions and the slow behaviour can be approximated with low-order moments. The three steps of the moment map method are inherited from the equation-free method, as discussed in great depth in [23]. The lifting and restricting steps can be interpreted as two operators that are projections between the macroscopic (slow behaviour or moment space) and microscopic (fast behaviour or single time simulations) levels.

As with the equation-free definition, the evolution of the moment map (slow system) is governed by an unknown expression that can be estimated through simulations of individual trajectories. Note that the governing equation of these single trajectories is known here but it can be acquired from measured signals as well. The stochastically disturbed system with a normal distribution in the excitation inherits the distribution for a short time because of the locally symmetric spreading of the evolved states. This is true for only the first-order moment map, where we consider the Dirac measure and the moment map is defined by the average of single simulations. On the other hand, the second-order moment map does not preserve the above-mentioned symmetry as the simulations are initiated with a Gaussian distribution in the states. Then the new state is calculated as for the previous case, but the variance of the solutions is also stored at the simulation endpoints. Note that the Gaussian measure can also be projected to the first-order moment map, which is the state space here.

An additional difficulty compared to [26] is that the system investigated throughout this study is an oscillatory problem. While they seek the equilibrium solution of certain systems, our interest is to follow the periodic solutions of the vibration amplitude and phase with respect to the changing excitation frequency. That is, the *resonance curve*, which is not to be mistaken by the acquired FRF's (frequency response functions) from measured data since those FRF's are considered to be described by a linear system.

The application of the moment map method for the stochastically excited Duffing oscillator (Eq. (4)) will be discussed in the following. The three steps of the method are now in the same state space with the addition of the frequency ratio $\mathbf{X}_i := [x_i \ \dot{x}_i \ \lambda_i]^T$, where the index i denotes the time instance t_i .

The first step is the initialisation of the fast system evolution by the lifting operator. In the case of the first-order moment, the lifting operator \mathcal{L}_1 is the current state of the underlying system in the state space. The lifting operator for the second-order moment \mathcal{L}_2 on the other hand gives a random variable (notation: \sim) about the current state with normal distribution (notation: $N(\text{mean}, \text{variance})$) in both the x and \dot{x} directions. The mathematical formulation of these lifting operators can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}_1(\mathbf{X}_i) := [\xi_i \ \dot{\xi}_i \ \lambda_i]^T, \quad \xi_i := \mathbf{X}_i \tag{7}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_2(\mathbf{X}_i) := [\xi_i \ \dot{\xi}_i \ \lambda_i]^T, \quad \xi_i \sim N(\bar{\xi}_i, \sigma_d^2) \tag{8}$$

where \mathbf{X}_i is the current state $(x_i, \dot{x}_i, \lambda_i)$ and ξ_i is equivalent to the current state if the first order moment is considered $(\xi_i, \dot{\xi}_i, \lambda_i)$. However, ξ and $\dot{\xi}$ are random variables, normally distributed with σ_d^2 variance around $\bar{\xi}_i := \mathbf{X}_i$. The first- and second-order lifting operators are distinguished through their indices, respectively.

The next step is the evolution of the fast system, where the lifting operator initiates the single simulation trajectories, as shown in Fig. 1. The evolution step itself consists of multiple simulations that are initiated by the lifting operator. The time interval of the evolution step is noted as $t_{ev} \in [t_i, t_{i+1}]$, where i denotes the current state. Note that the evaluation time $t_{i+1} - t_i = T$ is also the time period of the forcing frequency. The states at the end of the evolution step are marked as $\xi_{i+1,k}$, where the index k refers to a single simulation trajectory, which is fundamentally the stroboscopic sampling of randomly initiated simulations.

The final step is the restriction (\mathcal{R}) of the evolved states. Here, the restriction is not changed with respect to the order of the moment map because the investigated map is the state space. Hence, the restriction operator can be formulated as

$$\mathcal{R}(\Psi_{i+1}) := \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_{i+1,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \dot{\xi}_{i+1,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_{i+1,k} \right]^T = \bar{\xi}_{i+1}, \tag{9}$$

$$\Psi_{i+1} := [\xi_{i+1,1} \ \xi_{i+1,2} \ \dots \ \xi_{i+1,n}]^T, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}^+, \tag{10}$$

where the new state in the moment map will be the average of the fast system solutions, since the average of the results will give the mean or expected value of the state distribution at time t_{i+1} . Fig. 1 is a visual interpretation of the transitions between the moment map and the simulations for the first- and second-order cases.

As an example for the first-order moment map, let the current state be $(x_0, \dot{x}_0, \lambda_0)$ at $t_i = t_0$ defined in the moment map. Then we use this state as an initial condition for every individual simulation in the evolution step with the operator $\mathcal{L}_1(\mathbf{X}_i)$, resulting in

$$[\xi_0 \ \dot{\xi}_0 \ \lambda_0]^T := \mathcal{L}_1(\mathbf{X}_0) = [x_0 \ \dot{x}_0 \ \lambda_0]^T. \tag{11}$$

Fig. 1. The visual representation of the moment map (equation-free) method for the stochastically excited $(F_{\text{stoch}}(t)/m\omega_n^2 = f_0 \cos(\lambda t) + \sigma W(t))$ Duffing oscillator. Starting the evolution of the moment map from the lifted X_i state results in the new state X_{i+1} at the time instant $t_{i+1} = t_i + T$ after restricting the single solutions. Panel (a) is the state space of the current state. Panels (b) and (c) are the evolutions of the lifted initial conditions $\mathcal{L}_1(X_i)$ or $\mathcal{L}_2(X_i)$. Panels (d) and (e) show the restricted new state X_{i+1} compared to the old one X_i .

Since the state evolution is known individually for samples $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and is described by Eq. (4), the states $(\xi_{1,k}, \dot{\xi}_{1,k}, \lambda_1)$ can be calculated at the time instant $t_{i+1} = t_i$ by using the EM method (Eq. (6)). Then one can simply restrict the simulation trajectories at t_i by using the operator $\mathcal{R}(\Psi_{i+1})$, which can be formulated as

$$[x_1 \quad \dot{x}_1 \quad \lambda_1]^T = \mathcal{R}(\Psi_1) = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_{1,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \dot{\xi}_{1,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_{1,k} \right]^T. \tag{12}$$

The solution $(x_1, \dot{x}_1, \lambda_1)$ is the new state at t_1 that can be marked on the moment map along with the previous $(x_0, \dot{x}_0, \lambda_0)$ state, as shown in Fig. 1.

Note that the same can be done for the second-order moment map, where only the lifting operator is changed from \mathcal{L}_1 to \mathcal{L}_2 . In that case, the initial condition will not be constant, but a random variable around the current state.

4. Numerical continuation

The numerical continuation of deterministic and stochastic systems is discussed in this section. First, the deterministic continuation will be introduced briefly and specifically for the Duffing oscillator. Second, the method for continuing the stochastically excited system is presented.

Here, we emphasise that neither of the individual steps of this method is new, but the way they are used here differs from previous approaches by focusing on the amplitude behaviour of the observed stochastically excited mechanical system. Although

Fig. 2. Visual representation about the steps of the pseudo-arclength continuation combined with the moment map method for a stochastically excited system. Here, the state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j}$ is the current guess for the next bifurcation point \mathbf{X}_{l+1} within the Newton iteration. First, we take the point $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j}$ from the state space to create the initial conditions either for the first- $\mathcal{L}_1(\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j})$ or second-order $\mathcal{L}_2(\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j})$ moment map. Then, the evolution and restriction steps can be done according to Fig. 1. The restricted solutions $\bar{\xi}_{l+1,i+1}$ can be used for the Newton iteration steps, which will lead to the next iteration state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j+1}$. Note, that within the moment map evolution i and $i + 1$ used for denoting the sampling time instances (t_i and $t_{i+1} = t_i + T$).

there are numerical and even measurement approaches for the deterministic continuation of the frequency-response behaviour of vibrating applications [19,46], the stochastic approach is not a popular topic in this field. The focus of this work is on stochastically excited structural vibrations, while most previous studies focus on the distribution of particles (such as in gas dynamics [26] or the phantom traffic model [23]), molecular predictions in biology [47,48] or predictions in chemistry [49]. Most of the mentioned studies are capable of investigating periodic and nonlinear systems, although the amplitude behaviour of the periodic solution is not discussed in those studies. When the amplitudes also have to be considered due to the oscillatory behaviour, the definitions and the procedure of the previously introduced methods have to be refined.

We note that there is a promising alternative approach, where deterministic continuation is extended to investigate stochastic processes by using Lyapunov equations for known problems, such as the predator–prey system space [29]. The idea of using some indicator for the overlapping probabilities for state changes is heavily used in Section 5 which is similar to the approach in [29]. However, our method differs from theirs in a few ways. First, our approach is based on the moment map method combined with the pseudo-arclength continuation and probability theory as an additional tool (e.g. Markov chains, distribution analysis, Monte Carlo simulations), while in [29], they extend the continuation method by using the definition of regions with an elliptic form that contains a high density of sample paths. Furthermore, in our study, we strongly build towards vibration problems, where an additional Markov chain is presented that provides the transition probabilities through the distances of the periodic solutions.

4.1. Deterministic numerical continuation

A common tool for bifurcation analysis is numerical continuation. Here, we consider only the pseudo-arclength method, which is well known and widely available in the literature. For the foundation and measurement applications see [17] or [19] as a few examples. In general, the continuation method is used to trace branches of non-linear system solutions in the form of

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}) = 0, \tag{13}$$

where, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ is the current state of the system, $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the vector of the bifurcation parameters and $f : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is continuously differentiable as many times as the particular problem requires. This is also called the *zero problem* in the vector \mathbf{x} .

In this study, the investigated vector is the state of the underlying system, noted as $\mathbf{x}_l = [x_l \quad \dot{x}_l]$, where l is the current state and \mathbf{x}_l is a periodic solution. That is, \mathbf{x}_l is the same in the t_i and t_{i+1} time instances, $\mathbf{x}_l(t_{i+1}) = \mathbf{x}_l(t_i)$, if they are one time period $T = t_{i+1} - t_i$ apart from each other. The bifurcation parameter set is now the frequency ratio λ_l which is a scalar parameter. The unique solution of this problem is guaranteed by the implicit function theorem, but it does not hold for saddle–node bifurcations or at fold points [19]. To overcome this problem, the pseudo-arclength method can be applied, where the bifurcation parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is changed with respect to the previous point during branch tracking, as visualised in Fig. 2.

The current and previous state can be used to generate a secant, which gives a first prediction for the next branch point at distance Δs , that is the state \mathbf{X}_{l+1}^* according to Fig. 2. From this point, a Newton iteration can be used to find the solution to the zero problem with the condition that the iteration must be in the normal direction compared to the secant. Note that in many continuation packages the tangent predictor is used instead of the secant method due to the fact that the tangent predictor is directly computed from the Jacobian [50].

Returning to the investigation of the Duffing oscillator, the $f(\mathbf{x}_l, \lambda_l)$ function for the deterministic zero problem can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{F}_j = \left[\left\langle \left(\mathbf{X}_{l+1}^* - \mathbf{X}_l \right), \left(\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j+1} - \mathbf{X}_{l+1}^* \right) \right\rangle \right], \tag{14}$$

where $\mathbf{F}_j = \mathbf{0}$ is the definition of the current zero problem for the Duffing oscillator with state $\mathbf{X}_{l,j} := [x_{l,j} \ \dot{x}_{l,j} \ \lambda_{l,j}]^T$ where $\lambda_{l,j}$ is the scalar bifurcation parameter. The state without $\lambda_{l,j}$ frequency ratio is observed as $\mathbf{x}_{l,j} := [x_{l,j} \ \dot{x}_{l,j}]^T$. The indices l and j are the running parameters for the calculated bifurcation states and for the Newton iteration, respectively. As for the general case of the pseudo-arclength continuation, here the normal direction for the iteration is defined through the last row in Eq. (14) by the scalar product of the predicted and already computed states, visually interpreted in Fig. 2.

The next iteration state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j+1}$ can now be calculated using the Newton iteration as

$$\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j+1} = \mathbf{X}_{l+1,j} + \mathbf{J}_j^{-1} \mathbf{F}_j, \tag{15}$$

where $\mathbf{J}_j := \nabla^T \mathbf{F}_j$ is the Jacobian matrix and ∇ is the nabla operator.

Based on this information, the continuation of the periodic orbit branches can be done for the Duffing oscillator. Fig. 3 shows the results of a pseudo-arclength continuation for the deterministic case alongside the stochastic results, which are discussed in Section 4.2.

4.2. Stochastic numerical continuation

As for any stochastic system, in the case of a stochastically excited Duffing oscillator, the continuation method itself does not differ from the deterministic one. Instead, the definition of the zero problem has to be modified according to the stochastic behaviour of the state evolution. For this reason, the equation-free method can be used to define the stochastic \mathbf{F}_j , where the states can be evolved according to the moment map method, described in Section 3.

Fig. 2 shows the visual interpretation of the idea behind the stochastic numerical continuation with the embedded moment map method. As noted before, there are some studies in this direction, but the investigation of structural vibrations in this sense has not been approached from the engineering point of view so far.

As for the deterministic case, the definition of the zero problem (which corresponds to the stationary solution) is necessary, where we consider the states to be in the moment map. Since the direct relation between two states is unknown, the nonlinear problem for the Newton iteration cannot be written in the form as it is in Eq. (14).

Three states ($\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j}, \mathbf{X}_l, \mathbf{X}_{l-1}$) have to be defined here with the help of the equation-free method. The prior and current states are simply inherited from the moment map, but the state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j}$ has to be approximated by the evolution of the moment map as it is discussed in Section 3. In other words, we take the previous points from the branch for the definition of the secant, and the iterated state in the Newton method is evolved by the first-order moment using $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ simulations of single trajectories. The restriction has to be performed at certain time instances, which are defined by the frequency ratio λ that originates from the harmonic forcing, also presented in Fig. 1. The stationary solution occurs when the restricted point is the same for any multiple of the forcing time period T [51,52].

Observing the moment map of a single state evolution in Fig. 2, shows that the zero problem in the stochastic case can be constructed by defining a vector \mathbf{v}_j between the current iteration state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j}$ and the evolved iteration state $\mathbf{X}_{l+1,j+1}$. Then the goal of the Newton iteration within the continuation method is to reduce the length of the newly introduced vector to zero ($\|\mathbf{v}_j\|_2 = 0$) while the iteration is normal to the secant. This leads to a periodic solution.

The mathematical formulation of \mathbf{F}_j as part of the stochastic zero problem:

$$\mathbf{F}_j = \left[\left\langle \left(\mathbf{X}_{l+1}^* - \mathbf{X}_l \right), \left(\mathcal{R}(\Psi_{l+1,i+1}) - \mathbf{X}_{l+1}^* \right) \right\rangle \right], \tag{16}$$

$$\mathcal{R}(\Psi_{l+1,i}) := \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_{l+1,i,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \dot{\xi}_{l+1,i,k} \right]^T, \tag{17}$$

$$\mathcal{R}(\Psi_{l+1,i}) := \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_{l+1,i,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \dot{\xi}_{l+1,i,k} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_{l+1,i,k} \right]^T, \tag{18}$$

where Ψ is the collection of the end states from the evolution step, where the γ parameter is excluded from the data. The first row is the definition of the vector \mathbf{v}_j , and the last row provides the normal iteration direction as previously. Then the zero problem can be defined as $\mathbf{F}_j := f(\mathbf{x}_l, \gamma_l) = 0$, where the Newton iteration formally matches with Eq. (15).

Consequently, the key step in the continuation method is the definition of the vector \mathbf{F}_j , where the stochastic process is constructed. Moreover, the initialisation of the evolution step defines the order of the moment map [26]. According to the definition of the Dirac $\mathcal{L}_1(\mathbf{x}_{l+1,j})$ and Gaussian $\mathcal{L}_2(\mathbf{x}_{l+1,j})$ measures, one can continue either the first- or the second-order moment map as is discussed in Section 3.

The major issue dealing with the continuation of the underlying stochastically excited system is the computation cost because of the large sample size that is needed for the averaging during the restriction step. When the investigated bifurcation diagram is complex and sensitive to small perturbations, the sample size is required to be similarly large. This can easily lead to an explosion in computational time. However, there are some tools that can be used to reduce the time consumption of these simulations. One

Fig. 3. Row 1: results of the numerical continuation for different damping ratios ζ . The continuous line is from the deterministic system, while the dashed line is from the Dirac measure. Row 2: results of the numerical continuation for different sampling times. Here, the Gaussian measure is used. Row 3: results of the numerical continuation for approximate solutions for the Gaussian measure compared to the Dirac measure. The second column is the $\lambda - x$ projection of the state bifurcation and the third column shows the resonance curves. The first column shows the lifting method and the sampling time interval in row b). The nonlinear parameter $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$ and $f_0 = 0.025 \mu\text{m}$ globally.

way to do this is to use Broyden’s method [53,54] to update the Jacobian matrix during the Newton iteration. This will prevent the need to calculate the vector \mathbf{F}_j multiple times during one iteration step.

The final step is to calculate the amplitude behaviour while continuing the bifurcation in the moment map. This is simply done by averaging the amplitudes from the time-scale simulations after collecting the maximum and minimum state values. Thus, the calculation can be done with

$$A_{l+1} := \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{k=1}^n \max(\xi_{l+1,i+1,k}) - \min(\xi_{l+1,i+1,k}), \tag{19}$$

where l is the current bifurcation point, i is the running index for the stroboscopic time steps in the moment map, k is the running index of the current sample number, and $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is the sample size. Then the amplitude of the state \mathbf{X}_{l+1} can be defined by the amplitude definition A_{l+1} .

Fig. 3 shows both the first-order and second-order moment solutions of the stochastic continuation method projected in the state space and the $\lambda - A$ plane. As is shown for the equilibrium case in [26], here the first-order moment results for the periodic orbits are also indistinguishable from the deterministic solution for short time samples and low noise levels. On the other hand, the reduction of the bifurcation branch can be observed, when it is calculated from the second-order moment map. This also fits our expectations.

Since the stochastic continuation method with the first-order moment gives results close to the deterministic case for short-time samples and low noise levels, the behaviour of the underlying stochastic system can be approximated by the deterministic case for reasonably small noise levels in short-term processes. This is important for structural vibratory measurements for reliability reasons. Usually, measurements are based on the assumption that the excitation is purely harmonic, but in most cases, this is not entirely true. With the stochastic continuation method presented in this study, we can check or confirm about a specific measurement if it represents the actual deterministic system. Although this is an important remark, the major goal of this study is not about the deterministic system, but the investigation of stochastic behaviour.

As mentioned, the second-order moment must be considered for the analysis of the stochastic behaviour, where the continuation method becomes sensitive for the initial distribution of the states due to the properties of the Gaussian measure that is well

Fig. 4. Comparison between the varying operation time and noise amplitude (σ) considering the second-order moment map. (a) is a visual description of the results in the other panels. Panel (a) and (b) shows the system sensitivity for the various observation times and noise levels. The nonlinear parameter $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$ and $f_0 = 0.025 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ globally.

documented in [26]. In this study, the initial values of the single evolutions are defined by the Gaussian distribution, where we pick the neighbouring points of the previous iteration state (\mathcal{L}_2). The boundary of the neighbouring set is a circle, defined in the plane of the two-dimensional state space (x, \hat{x}) also shown in Fig. 3c. The mean value is the centre of the circle (previous state), and the boundary radius is defined by the standard deviation σ_d as an approximation for the Gaussian measure.

There are several properties of the second-order moment map continuation that have to be discussed. The first and most visible is that with increasing noise level, the bifurcation structure changes as it is shown in Fig. 4. The second property is related to the time interval of the stroboscopic mapping, where we can wait several time periods before sampling. As this time grows, the bifurcation tends to deviate more and more compared to the deterministic case, similarly to the reaction for the noise level increase. This is due to the strong connection between the probability of losing stability by overstepping the unstable boundary of the current stable periodic orbit and the elapsed simulation time. Although the changing noise amplitude shows similar behaviour as the varying observation time, we note that in a realistic situation one has insignificant control over the noise level, while the operational time depends on the user. Therefore, the analysis of the time dependence seems to be more appropriate. The question is then, how one can describe the stochastic system behaviour when the stability is time-dependent and also sensitive to the level of the introduced noise? This problem is addressed in Section 5.

We note that to save simulation time costs, in some cases, the normal distribution is replaced by evenly distributed points from a given distance around the mean, as Fig. 3 shows. The distance is defined by the standard deviation σ of the noise introduced. Note that the results show a good match with the normally distributed simulations.

Assuming that there is a bistable section in a deterministic system, we know that for small perturbations within the attraction of one stable periodic orbit, the solution with time will tend to remain within the attraction of that domain. Unfortunately, this is not inherited by the stochastic system. As soon as some level of noise is introduced through the excitation, the escape of the solution is just a matter of time [29]. This is called *metastability* (discussed in Section 5) and the investigation of this time-dependent property is a key point in the interpretation of the stochastic bifurcation analysis. To overcome the limitation of the moment map due to time-dependent stability loss, a semi-analytical approach is introduced in Section 5.2 alongside a procedure that is hoped to be used as a measurement method in the future.

5. Metastability and the first passage time

In this section, the transformation of the bistable region into a metastable region is discussed. Moreover, the mean first passage time is introduced as a new interpretation of the stability of periodic orbits in structural vibrations. The combination of the deterministic continuation method with a proper Markov chain can be used for the approximation of the stochastic behaviour similarly to the ellipse method [29]. Here, we differ from the ellipse method by defining sections on the deterministic resonance curve to define the transition probabilities within a Markov chain.

Also, speaking of stability in stochastic systems is often difficult and leads to misunderstanding due to the time-dependent sensitivity of the stability. Therefore, we introduce some definitions for a better understanding, which will be used in this section.

Unlike in the case of the deterministic Duffing oscillator, where the stability of the periodic motion can be decided based on only the initial conditions, the observation time of the process and the introduced level of noise also have to be considered in the stochastic case. In deterministic systems, one can tell the exact initial parameters for operating the given system as intended when observing a bistable region. This implies for the Duffing oscillator that one can initiate motion on a higher or a lower amplitude stable periodic oscillation within the bistable region.

Here, the *basin of attraction* (BOA) [55–57] describes the system well regardless of the observation time, but for stochastic processes, the BOA will change with the observation time. Note that for the deterministic case the BOA provides important information about the transient behaviour of a system. Calculating the settling time and the stable initial condition set is often important in investigating lightly damped systems. The settling time can be told exactly for a deterministic system initialised in a specific state.

Unfortunately, stochastic excitation takes away this property of the system due to the introduced Wiener process (Section 2). Looking at the normal distribution, it is clear that there is a certain probability of a critical perturbation in the case of the Duffing

Fig. 5. Sketch (a) shows the Markov chain of the introduced stochastically excited Duffing oscillator. Sketch (b) is the structural representation of the two stable periodic orbits after the transition from the higher orbit to the lower one. Panel (c) represents this transition for a set of stochastic simulations (grey envelope) compared to a deterministic one (blue line). The red and yellow trajectories are two example simulation results from the total evaluation set. The stochastic and system parameters are $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$, $\sigma = 0.015 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $\zeta = 0.04$, $f_0 = 0.025 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

oscillator for which it will be attracted by the other attractor in the bistable region. As the oscillation progresses in time, the chance of reaching this critical perturbation increases. Thus, the region is not considered to be bistable but metastable due to time dependence [32,58,59].

The question is then, how the stability of the periodic orbits can be defined. The deterministic system and the first-order moment solution definitions will be called stable and unstable periodic orbits as before. However, the stability of the stochastic system behaviour within the metastable region requires some clarification. A periodic orbit is called stable in the stochastic system (regarding the second-order moment map) if the periodic solution in question is stable throughout the observation time. In other words, the current state of the system is stable in the stochastic vibration sense if there is no state change throughout the observed time interval. The critical time instance, when the periodic orbit loses its stability, is called *mean first passage time* (MFPT: τ) [30–32], which can be calculated from the Markov chain for the stochastic system [27,28]. While Section 5.2 is a detailed discussion about this Markov chain and the approximation of τ , Section 5.1 is a practical approach to calculating the MFPT based on individual simulations.

5.1. Numerical approximation of the first passage time

The first approach to the calculation and understanding of the MFPT (τ) for the stochastic Duffing oscillator presented is through individual simulations.

Here, the idea is to run a large number of simulations, where we try to detect the first state change if one occurs. As mentioned above, the two states are the higher and lower amplitude periodic oscillations within the metastable region, shown in Fig. 5. After finding the individual transition times for the simulations of single trajectories, we can deduce some important information about the stability of periodic solutions in the bifurcation diagram. Namely, the likelihood of transitioning to the other state for the first time. Also, the mode and the distribution of the detected transition times can be stored, from which the deterministic continuation can be modified according to the stochastic behaviour. Note that the results from the single evolutions might not cover the whole deviation of the investigated MFPT as the simulations run until a given time instance. The processing of the individual simulations starts with calculating the amplitudes for every time period. This can be done using window functions or the Hilbert transform of the simulation [60]. In this way, one can observe which state the underlying system is currently in. The current state or amplitude can be interpreted as in Fig. 6. The only problem is that the state change is not a clear distinctive point in time, when one looks only at the amplitude of the oscillation.

To spot the amplitude transitions, one might think that the detection of crossing the unstable periodic orbit given by the deterministic system would be sufficient, but it does not work for the stochastic Duffing oscillator. This is due to the fluctuation introduced by the Wiener process around the stationary solution.

Fig. 7 shows a deterministic and a stochastic time simulation side by side considering the previously introduced 1 DoF model. Observing the amplitude and history of *perturbed oscillation frequency* (POF: ω_s), the transition behaviour of both nonlinear cases can be understood. In the deterministic case, the simulation starts near the fold on the higher-energy-level stable branch. A small perturbation in the initial conditions causes it to transit to the lower energy state. Since this is a transient solution, the oscillation settles through the backbone curve and then the POF transitions back to the stationary forcing frequency ω [13]. In contrast, when the same system is excited stochastically, the POF shows a rather different behaviour before and after the occurrence of the transition between the two states.

Fig. 6. Panels (a) and (b) both show the amplitude behaviour of the stochastically excited Duffing oscillator with respect to time. While on panel (a) the fluctuation of the transient oscillation is not considered, the fluctuation is included on panel (b). The correct detection of a state change occurs when the amplitude from a single simulation trajectory crosses the corresponding unstable periodic orbit on panel (b). Panels (i) to (v) are magnified examples from panel (b) for the state transition detection, while the sixth stochastic example remains stable throughout the entire observation time. The colouring is consistent, where the light blue line is the deterministic solution and all the other lines are stochastic samples. While the dashed lines note the unstable periodic solutions and the grey region is the envelope of these solutions, the green region is the envelope of the stochastic simulations. The stochastic and system parameters are $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$, $\sigma = 0.015 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $\zeta = 0.04$, $f_0 = 0.025 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Deterministic column, (i): a single simulation trajectory of a deterministic Duffing oscillator while transitioning from the higher energy state to the lower one. Stochastic columns, (ii) and (iii): The same observation for a stochastically excited Duffing oscillator. Row (a): simulation of single trajectories. Row (b) and (c): the transient oscillation frequency and amplitude behaviour during state transition. Note that the blue line refers to the deterministic case and the other colours are there for the stochastic simulations. Further to that, the envelope of the stochastic simulations is represented with grey shading. The 9 panels together show the relevance of considering the POF (ω_s) during state transition detection (Fig. 6). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. The proposed interpretation of the first passage time and efficient stochastic bifurcation analysis is presented here. Panels (c) and (d) show the first passage times at discrete values of the frequency ratio parameter λ that are related to the marked branches on panel (a). For every λ value, the distribution of the simulated samples is interpreted as waterfall diagrams (orange columns), where the mode is the most commonly observed value of a data set. Panel (b) is a constructed bifurcation diagram from panels (c) and (d). We consider this as the maximum degradation of the bifurcation since there are no transitions on the marked periodic orbits within a reasonable time. The stochastic and system parameters are $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$, $\sigma = 0.015 \mu\text{m}$, $\zeta = 0.04$, $f_0 = 0.025 \mu\text{m}$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Although fluctuation of the amplitude is expected since stochastic excitation is present in the system, fluctuation of the POF (Figs. 6, 7) must be explained. Here, the introduction of the Wiener process causes the system to temporarily leave the slow manifold [61,62], leading to a small fluctuation in both amplitude and frequency due to the appearance of the backbone behaviour. Thus, the system is moving slightly around the initial state on the bifurcation branch. When this behaviour is taken into account, the unstable boundary also fluctuates with the state. This has to be also embedded in the detection method of the state transition. Fig. 6 shows the amplitude behaviour with and without considering the fluctuation around the observed state.

Now, the construction of the first passage time can be done by collecting the transition times, detected from the single-simulation trajectories. Note that all of these simulations start from the same initial conditions. Fig. 8 is a proposed interpretation of the first passage time, where all transitions are observed at discrete values of λ . Marking all the transitions and the modes of the calculated data gives information about the likelihood of the transition and about when it might happen.

Note that the investigated periodic orbit is unconditionally stable (regarding the time) within the observed time frame if there is not a single solution which transits to the other state. The distribution of the transition times can also be observed, as shown in Fig. 8. In terms of processing these data, the outcome highly depends on the actual application. The mode and distribution of the simulated τ data set together lead to important information that will be used in Section 5.2.

Assume that we have a sensitive process which cannot be exposed to state changes under any circumstances within the time frame of 100 s. Imagine this as a machining process (without considering any delay and assuming strong nonlinearity), where the tool and the workpiece would also be destroyed during a state change. Here, it is necessary to mark all the periodic orbits as unstable that have gone through any transition during that 100 s. Fig. 8 shows a possible interpretation of the remaining stable periodic orbits in the bifurcation diagram as a shortening of the branches.

In other cases, where the state change is not as critical as was mentioned in the previous machining example, the modes of the data set can be considered to be the critical MFPT of the system. Stable periodic solutions of the deterministic bifurcation branches can be called stable until the calculated critical values, τ . After τ time, the observed periodic solution has a high possibility of changing state.

Using this method to approximate the suitable bifurcation diagram for the underlying system is much faster than the calculation of the second-order moment continuation for a given observation time frame. Thus, the mean first passage time can be a useful property in engineering due to having processes with given time frames.

Fig. 9. Panel (a) is the visual interpretation of deriving the transition probabilities of certain state changes. Here, δ_{11} is the section related to the probability of not changing state starting from *state 1*. The same is true for δ_{22} but for *state 2*. Then, the probabilities for the Markov chain (panel b) and the MFPT can be calculated by comparing these sections to the standard deviation of the Wiener process (σ) and going through the steps, visualised in panel (c).

5.2. Theoretical approximation of the first passage time

A semi-analytical approach to calculating the mean first passage time is presented here through a Markov chain. These models are generally used in probability calculations about systems where the future state variable has to be predicted based on the current conditions. The Markov chain is also used to define the Fokker–Planck–Kolmogorov equation, mentioned in Section 3. The most common way of introducing Markov chain-based systems is through weather forecast examples, behavioural expectations, or market predictions [63–66].

In general, the Markov chain consists of different states that describe the behaviour of the system and the transition probabilities of moving from one state to another (categorical changes in wind power [65] or in our case transitions between periodic solutions). Thus, it can be interpreted through a graph in which the nodes are the states and the connections are the transition probabilities.

There are well-developed methods to calculate the probability of visiting a state later in time and calculate the MFPT between two specific states [30]. In this section, these methods are used in a unique manner for the introduced structural vibratory problem, where the goal is to calculate the mean first passage times for certain excitation angular frequencies. This is for the approximation of the stochastic resonance curve of the underlying system.

First, a specific Markov chain must be created for this study, which is introduced for discrete λ , dimensionless excitation frequencies. Fig. 8 shows that there exist two stable states in the deterministic bistable region for any λ that becomes metastable once the stochastic term is introduced to the excitation. Here, *state 1* denotes the higher energy level periodic orbit solution and *state 2* marks the lower one. Based on [30], the matrix representation and the mean first passage time $\tau_{i,k}$ of the current Markov chain can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

$$\tau_{i,2} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^2 p_{ik} \tau_{k,2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{P} is the transition probability matrix. The first indices of the elements mark the current state, and the second ones refer to the visited state. Index i denotes the initial state and $\tau_{i,2}$ measures the average or expected time periods needed for transitioning to *state 2* from *state i* for the first time. The question then is the transition probabilities (\mathbf{P}) between the two states in order to calculate $\tau_{i,2}$.

As mentioned before, Markov chains can show the reachable states of the underlying system at given time instances in the future. These time instances are strongly connected to the stroboscopic mapping here as the state transition is detected through the state deviation at the beginning and at the end of the oscillation time period. Thus, one step in time is considered equal to the time period of the harmonic forcing. During a single step, the mean of the oscillation and the deviation are equivalent to the properties of the introduced Wiener process in the forcing. Although assuming normal distribution throughout the whole investigated time period is not exactly true, for our purpose and small noise levels, it is a sufficient approximation. Thus, the numerical value 1 in Eq. (21) represents one time period (T) of the harmonic forcing and the transition probabilities are deduced from the deterministic nonlinear resonance curves calculated in Section 4. However, in reality, measuring the unstable periodic orbits is hardly achievable or even possible. Therefore, another forcing-based quantification of the desired δ_{ik} values is also shown at the end of this section.

Fig. 9 shows the process of picking the correct sections from the continued resonance curve to calculate the transition probabilities. As an example for the calculation of the stability *state 1*, these sections are indicated by $\delta_{11}/2$, which can be compared to the deviation of the stochastic forcing σ . Here, the indices of δ_{ik} refer to the same transitions as the indices in the transition probability matrix \mathbf{P} . Note that the picked section is doubled because the amplitude is just half of the full displacement during one oscillation.

The calculation of the transition probability is calculated through the δ_{ik} sections compared to the normal distribution with $\bar{\mu}$ mean value and σ deviation. The fundamentals of the normal distribution and the way in which one can calculate the probability

Fig. 10. Panels (a) and (b) are comparisons between the numerical and semi-analytical calculations of the MFPT for different system parameters (μ and ζ). The coloured regions are the semi-analytical (red) solution compared to the critical modes from the numerical case (blue). The dashed lines are fitted curves for the coloured regions for better comparability between the solutions of the two methodologies. The value λ^* refers to the critical point, where the otherwise stable branch becomes unstable above or below this value, depending on which bifurcation branch is observed. Here, the upper branch becomes unstable above the value λ^* . Panel (c) represents the effect of changing the parameters and the reduction of the upper periodic orbit is also shown for a specific case. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of getting a certain value within the δ_{ik} interval (Fig. 9) are well documented in [67]. In this study, it looks as follows. First, we can write the cumulative distribution function and the error function, respectively, as

$$\Phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-t^2/2} dt, \tag{22}$$

$$\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt. \tag{23}$$

Then the cumulative distribution function can be expressed with the error function as

$$\Phi(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \text{erf} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \right). \tag{24}$$

The variable of the function Φ can be extended with the mean of the data set $\bar{\mu}$ and the standard deviation σ of the normal distribution, which will formally lead to

$$F(x) = \Phi \left(\frac{x - \bar{\mu}}{\sigma} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \text{erf} \left(\frac{x - \bar{\mu}}{\sigma\sqrt{2}} \right) \right). \tag{25}$$

Now, the probability of getting a value in the interval $[-n\sigma, n\sigma]$, $n \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is

$$p = F(\bar{\mu} + n\sigma) - F(\bar{\mu} - n\sigma) = \text{erf} \left(\frac{n}{\sqrt{2}} \right). \tag{26}$$

In the case of this study, the value of n is defined by the δ_{ik} sections as $\delta_{ik} = n\sigma$. This enables the calculation of the transition probabilities:

$$p_{11} = \text{erf} \left(\frac{\delta_{11}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right), \tag{27}$$

$$p_{12} = 1 - p_{11}, \tag{28}$$

where p_{12} is the transition probability between *state 1* and *state 2*, starting from *state 1*. Then based on Eq. (21) and (27) the mean first passage time for the *state 1* → *state 2* transition can be derived as

$$\bar{\tau}_{1,2} = \tau_{1,2}T = \frac{T}{1 - p_{11}} = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda\omega_n \left(1 - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{\delta_{11}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right) \right)}, \tag{29}$$

where both δ_{11} and δ_{22} change as the value λ changes within the metastable region. The T forcing time period is there to calculate the MFPT in seconds and $\bar{\tau}_{1,2}$ is the semi-analytical approximation of the modes in Fig. 8.

Fig. 10 is the visual representation of how the critical value λ^* varies when the nonlinear parameter μ or the damping ratio ζ of the underlying system is changed. The λ^* denotes the critical point on the stable branch from where the previously stable high-amplitude orbits will become unstable after some time (predefined time interval, here it is 10^4 s). The solutions of the semi-analytical method can be compared with the numerical results, as shown in Fig. 8. Here, the main connection between the two methods is the mode of the numerical data set and the approximate mean first passage times from the theoretical calculations. As the mode of the numerical data turns into exponential growth, similarly, the theoretical approximation follows this characteristic. Based on these results, the deterministic bifurcation diagram can be shortened to the point where the mean first passage time $\bar{\tau}_{i,k}$ exceeds the value $10^4 - 10^5$ considering that structural vibratory problems usually do not last longer than this value.

The results show a strong connection between the two methods when the damping ratio is relatively low. However, the results differ slightly from each other for larger damping ratios, as Fig. 10 shows.

As mentioned above, the measurement of unstable periodic orbits is often questionable. Therefore, a method for defining the δ_{ik} sections is presented here. To determine these sections, the deterministic system is forced to a state on the lower stable branch. The system then receives a burst excitation in the form of $CF_0 \cos(\lambda t)$ for the time interval δt instead of the $\sigma W(t)$ expression in Eq. (4). For growing C , multiple single trajectories are simulated, where the observed transient state and the final state are in question. As the C constant reaches a critical level C_{cr1} , the system moves to the state of the upper branch. Then the C constant is increased even further until the system goes back to the lower periodic orbit (C_{cr2}). The two critical C values can then be compared to the measured stable periodic orbits, from which the δ_{ik} values can be calculated. First, the ratio of the critical constants has to be calculated as

$$C_{rat} = \frac{C_{cr1}}{C_{cr2}}. \tag{30}$$

Then the amplitude difference between the two deterministically stable periodic orbits for a given λ has to be calculated from a measured bifurcation analysis as

$$A_{dif} = A_{up} - A_{low}, \tag{31}$$

where A_{up} and A_{low} are the amplitudes of the upper and lower periodic orbits for a given λ . From there the sought section can be calculated starting on the upper periodic orbit (*state 1*) as

$$\delta_{11} = A_{dif}C_{rat}. \tag{32}$$

Substituting the δ_{11} value into Eq. (27), and by going through Eqs. (28) and (29) the MFPT can be calculated. The results of this method compared to the sections from the unstable periodic orbits are presented in Fig. 11.

Although the solutions from the semi-analytical method (with both definitions δ_{ik}) differ slightly from the numerical results, they remain relatively close to the simulation outcome from the engineering point of view. Furthermore, the theoretical calculations show similar characteristics in all cases. Thus, the semi-analytical method can be considered a good approximation that saves simulation costs. The time consumption of both the stochastic numerical continuation and the numerical MFPT calculation can sometimes be measured in days or weeks. However, calculations with the semi-analytical method can be done in just a few seconds.

6. Conclusion and discussion

The focus of this study is to show that nonlinear structures under combined harmonic and stochastic excitations can behave properly to establish an applicable measurement methodology. In engineering applications such as machining, the connection between the vibration amplitude and the forcing frequency is a critical property for describing a stable and effective machining process. Therefore, the effect of the inevitable occurrence of noise through the random (stochastic) forcing is a key feature to be analysed considering both linear and nonlinear cases.

Using a simple ideal structure with geometric nonlinearity, we demonstrate that the proposed combined calculation process is capable of capturing the dynamic properties of the underlying system. Here, the combination of the continuation method with multi-level simulation practises and statistical analysis results in a compact methodology that aims to be the foundation of future measurement applications regarding the quantification of nonlinear dynamic characteristics.

In this paper, the numerical continuation of a stochastically excited one-degree-of-freedom mechanical system has been achieved by using the moment map method for periodic solutions, where the amplitude behaviour is in importance. Investigating the first- and second-order moment maps, the effect of the introduced noise in the excitation can be observed as the bifurcation of the deterministic system differs from the one for the stochastic system. Note that the calculation of these modified bifurcation diagrams (that represents the amplitude-forcing behaviour) is numerically expensive (can be measured in weeks). To overcome the high calculation cost of the bifurcation diagrams, the deterministic case has been extended with a probabilistic method through the

Fig. 11. Panels (i) show single deterministic trajectories in time, where the forcing in Eq. (4) is completed with an additional $C F_0 \cos(\lambda t)$ burst excitation for δt time interval instead of the Wiener process. In panels (ii) the phase portrait of the single trajectories are shown. Panels (iii) compares the MFPT from the original Markov chain (black line) with the MFPT from the measurement related Markov chain (purple line) and with the numerical simulations (blue dots, where the modes are denoted by green circles). Rows (a) to (c) show examples for different μ . The nonlinear parameter values are $\mu = 0.275 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$, $\mu = 0.375 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ 1}/\mu\text{m}^2$ respectively from row (a) to (c). The other system parameters are $\zeta = 0.04$, $f_0 = 0.025 \mu\text{m}$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

introduction of Markov chains. Here, using the MFPT between two stable states, the deviation of the bifurcation diagram from the deterministic case can be calculated for a given operation time with a given noise level. First, a numerical study has been developed with the realisation of the fluctuation in the forcing frequency due to the transient nature of the stochastically excited system. Here, the detection method of a state transition has been introduced, where the initialisation of the stochastic simulation trajectories is based on the deterministic bifurcation diagram. Once a trajectory goes through a state change, the time instant of the transition is stored and by using statistical analysis the mean of the transition times can be calculated, which is then introduced as the MFPT. However, this method can also be time-consuming, and the physical application might be questionable in some cases. Therefore, a semi-analytical methodology has been derived, which is based on the amplitude differences of the periodic solutions with the same forcing frequency, Section 5.2. Here, the measurement of unstable periodic orbits is questionable from the practical point of view. However, the mentioned amplitude differences can be approximated also by the ratio of sinusoidal burst forcing levels, where state transition occurs, as a foundation for possible future measurements for the MFPT. The parameter sensitivity analysis has shown that the numerical and semi-analytical solutions slightly differ in some cases (e.g. for larger damping ratios), but the characteristics are the same.

The main drawback when investigating stochastic bifurcation diagrams (response for the random forcing) is that it changes with the operation time. It is especially time-consuming when the bifurcation analysis has to be done by numerical continuation since it would be necessary to calculate the diagrams for multiple operation times. Although the numerical MFPT computation can also be time-consuming for long operations, it is still incomparably faster than the continuation method. In addition, the semi-analytical Markov chain can give fast approximations for the stability of periodic orbits. However, the phase of the vibration has to be also considered to further improve the proposed methodology in the future.

Future works are expected to extend the methodology into measurement practises and investigate more complex structural vibration problems. Furthermore, the calculation of the state transition probability with a certain confidence interval might be the basis for some failure or reliability predictions in engineering applications [24].

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zoltan Gabos: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualisation. **David A.W. Barton:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Zoltan Dombovari:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The necessary data (parameters) are provided in the article to recreate the results.

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